

GRAMMAR PROFICIENCY IN ENGLISH AS A SECOND LANGUAGE (ESL) AS BASIS FOR SYNTAX LEARNING BOOKLET

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ABSTRACT

Grammar is a fundamental component of language proficiency, serving as the foundation for effective communication in both written and spoken forms. It enables learners to construct clear and meaningful sentences, facilitating comprehension and interaction. However, for English as a Second Language (ESL) learners, mastering grammar presents significant challenges, often leading to persistent errors that hinder language development. Recognizing these difficulties, this study investigates the grammar proficiency of Grade VII ESL learners from Tuyongan Integrated School and Gama Integrated School, focusing on key grammatical areas such as subject-verb agreement, verb tenses, prepositions, and pronouns. The study's respondents consisted of 136 Grade VII students, selected through purposive sampling. Using a researcher-made multiple-choice grammar assessment, the study evaluates students' proficiency levels and explores the influence of demographic factors, including sex, monthly family income, and access to English learning materials. Findings indicate that while students demonstrate varying levels of proficiency, common grammatical errors persist, particularly in verb tense usage and subject-verb agreement. Statistical analysis reveals significant differences in proficiency based on demographic factors, underscoring the need for targeted instructional interventions. To address these gaps, the study develops a Syntax Learning Booklet (SLB), designed as a supplementary tool incorporating structured lessons, explicit explanations, and contextualized practice exercises. By aligning with best practices in ESL instruction, this study aims to enhance students'

grammatical competence, ultimately improving their academic performance and communication skills.

Keywords: *Grammar Proficiency, Syntax Learning Booklet, Integrated Schools, ESL*

INTRODUCTION

English occupies a prominent role in the Philippines, shaping key sectors such as education, commerce, and administration. Despite its widespread use and the country's status as one of Asia's largest English-speaking nations, studies suggest a decline in English proficiency, particularly in writing skills (Sioco & De Vera, 2018). This trend presents significant challenges for learners, as English continues to hold increasing importance in both education and employment opportunities (Renandya et al., 2018). Grammar proficiency, as a core component of English language skills, is critical for effective communication and academic success, serving as the foundation for advanced language capabilities. However, many English as a Second Language (ESL) learners face persistent difficulties with grammatical accuracy, particularly in areas such as verb affixation, pronouns, prepositions, and subject-verb agreement (Tanpoco et al., 2019). These issues are evident among learners at Tuyongan and Gama Integrated Schools in the District of Calinog I, as diagnostic tests and essay writing assessments have revealed significant grammar deficiencies among Grade VII students.

The transition to secondary education introduces learners to more complex English structures, creating a need for additional grammatical support. Limited resources and diverse student populations further complicate efforts to enhance grammar proficiency in these integrated schools. Moreover, Madrunio et al. (2016) underscored that traditional grammar instruction often remains theoretical and disconnected from practical applications, necessitating the adoption of more contextualized and relevant teaching methods.

In the context of ESL education, grammar plays a pivotal role in communication, academic achievement, and career development. As noted by Adwani & Shrivastava (2017), various factors such as age, motivation, learning styles, access to learning materials, and interference from the native language influence the acquisition of grammar skills among ESL learners. Halliday's Systemic Functional Grammar theory, elaborated by Halliday and Matthiessen (2015), further emphasizes that grammatical choices are shaped by communication goals and social contexts, advocating for a blend of formal instruction and functional approaches to enhance grammar proficiency.

To address these challenges, effective ESL materials should be contextualized, culturally responsive, and tailored to meet learners' specific needs and proficiency levels. Tomlinson (2011) emphasized that while textbooks remain essential resources, multimodal materials incorporating real-life language use and digital technology are increasingly effective. Interactive and adaptable digital resources further support

individualized learning, offering formative feedback and enhancing engagement (Han, et., al. 2024).

Despite these insights, existing studies highlight gaps in addressing the specific grammar challenges faced by Grade VII learners in under-resourced integrated schools. While form-focused instruction integrated with meaningful language use has been acknowledged as important, there remains a lack of tailored resources, particularly in the context of online and blended learning as stated in the study conducted by Alvarez (2020). This situation underscores the pressing need for targeted solutions to improve grammar proficiency among ESL learners.

Aligned with this perspective, the present study emphasizes the importance of tailoring grammar instruction to meet learners' specific needs. To address these challenges, the study aimed to assess the grammar proficiency of Grade VII ESL learners in Tuyongan and Gama Integrated Schools and subsequently developed a Syntax Learning Booklet to enhance their skills. The booklet was specifically designed to bridge the gap between theoretical learning and practical language use by incorporating explicit explanations, structured activities, and contextualized practice exercises. Serving as supplementary instructional material, the booklet offers learners practice activities, sample exercises, and real-life applications that directly address their grammatical weaknesses in areas such as subject-verb agreement, verb tense, prepositions, and pronouns.

This approach reflects insights from research advocating for adaptable and context-sensitive grammar teaching methods (Aown, 2023). Furthermore, the implications of this study extend beyond the immediate context of Tuyongan and Gama Integrated Schools. The findings and instructional strategies proposed in the Syntax Learning Booklet have broader applicability to the Philippine education system, particularly as the country moves toward a global economy where English proficiency plays an increasingly vital role in education, communication, and professional opportunities. By combining theoretical grammar instruction with meaningful and practical applications, this study contributes to the advancement of ESL education in under-resourced schools and provides valuable insights for addressing the grammar challenges faced by learners nationwide.

Research Questions

This study aimed to assess the grammar proficiency of Grade VII ESL learners of Tuyongan and Gama Integrated School for the School Year 2024-2025 and use the findings as a basis for developing a Syntax Learning Booklet.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What was the level of grammar proficiency among the respondents as a whole and when categorized according to sex, monthly family income, and number of English language materials used?

2. Was there a significant difference in the level of grammar proficiency among the respondents when categorized according to sex, monthly family income, and number of English language materials used?
3. Based on the findings, what components were included in the Syntax Learning Booklet to address the identified grammar challenges?

METHODOLOGY

Participants

The study involved 136 Grade 7 learners from Tuyongan and Gama Integrated Schools in the District of Calinog I of the school year 2024–2025. This population included learners with varying levels of grammar proficiency, providing a comprehensive basis for evaluating their grammatical strengths and weaknesses. Grade 7 learners were chosen as they are at a crucial stage in secondary education where foundational English grammar skills are developed and expanded, making them ideal for assessing grammar proficiency.

Research Instrument

The study utilized a researcher-made multiple-choice English grammar assessment tool that assessed the grammar proficiency of Grade VII ESL learners. The instrument focused on four key areas: subject-verb agreement, verb tenses, prepositions, and pronouns through 60 questions evenly distributed across these topics to provide a comprehensive evaluation.

The test consisted of two sections: the first gathered demographic data, including sex, monthly family income, and the number of English learning materials used, while the second assessed grammar proficiency. Questions were designed progressively to match varying competency levels.

The instrument was expert-validated, pilot-tested, and statistically analyzed, yielding a reliability coefficient of 0.831, ensuring its consistency. The final assessment results formed the basis for developing the Syntax Learning Booklet, addressing the major grammatical weaknesses identified and providing a tailored resource to support learning.

Data Gathering Procedure

The data collection followed systematic and ethical research procedures (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). Before conducting this study, the researcher obtained permission from the authorities of the Schools Division of Iloilo, Schools District of Calinog I, and Tuyongan and Gama Integrated Schools. After the research-made instrument was approved and validated, parental consent forms were distributed to students and parents, outlining the study's purpose, assessment type, and data confidentiality. The researcher then conducted a pilot test at Pandan Integrated School. Furthermore, when the result of the

pilot test was determined, the researcher distributed another set of parental consent forms and personally administered the English Grammar Proficiency Assessment Tool to the target respondents. All completed assessments were securely stored for analysis. Moreover, data were analyzed based on predefined rating scales to identify grammar proficiency trends and relationships with demographic factors.

Data Analysis Procedure

The data from the English Grammar Proficiency Assessment Tool, administered to 136 Grade 7 students from Tuyongan and Gama Integrated Schools in Calinog, were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The descriptive analysis, focusing on the Mean, assessed overall grammar proficiency and highlighted strengths and weaknesses in subject-verb agreement, verb tenses, prepositions, and pronouns. Additionally, inferential statistics were employed to test the study's hypotheses: The Mann-Whitney U test was used to determine significant differences in grammar proficiency when respondents were classified by sex and the number of English language materials used. The Kruskal-Wallis test analyzed differences in grammar proficiency among respondents categorized by monthly family income.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Descriptive Data Analysis

Grammar Proficiency of the Respondents

Table 1 shows that the grammar proficiency of the respondents as an entire group, the male respondents, those respondents with the following Monthly Family Income of 10,000 and below, above 20,000, and those who has 1-2 learning materials used is “Satisfactory” with Means ranging from 31.33 to 35.19. While the female respondents, those with a Monthly Family Income of 10,001-20,000 and those who has 3 and more learning materials used has “Very Satisfactory” level of grammar proficiency with Means ranging from 36.33 to 37.49.

According to Madrunio et al. (2016), limited resources and diverse student populations further complicate efforts to enhance grammar proficiency. This suggests that the grammar proficiency levels of respondents are influenced by factors such as gender, monthly family income, and access to learning materials.

Table 1
Grammar Proficiency of the Respondents

Category	N	Mean	Description
Entire Group	136	34.91	Satisfactory
Sex			
Male	65	33.35	Satisfactory
	465		

Female	71	36.33	Very Satisfactory
Monthly Family Income			
10000 and below	90	35.19	Satisfactory
10001-20000	24	36.58	Very Satisfactory
Above 20000	22	31.95	Satisfactory
Number of Learning Materials			
1-2	87	33.46	Satisfactory
3 and more	49	37.49	Very Satisfactory
Scale	Description		
1.00 – 12.00	Poor		
12.01 – 24.00	Fair		
24.01 – 36.00	Satisfactory		
36.01 – 48.00	Very Satisfactory		
48.01 – 60.00	Excellent		

Inferential Data Analysis

Mann-Whitney Test Result for the Differences in the Grammar Proficiency of the Respondents when Classified as to Sex and Learning Materials Used

Mann-Whitney results in Table 2 showed a significant difference in the grammar proficiency of the respondents when they are classified as to sex ($z=2.030$; $p=.042$) and number of learning materials used ($z=2.686$; $p=.007$). The p-values are less than 0.05, therefore the null hypothesis in this regard is rejected. This indicates that the respondents' differences in their sex and number of learning materials used significantly influence their grammar proficiency.

As Adwani and Shrivastava (2017) highlighted, factors like learning styles, motivation, and access to resources play crucial roles in language acquisition. Female respondents, who achieved higher proficiency, may benefit from different learning approaches or stronger motivation. Additionally, respondents with three or more learning materials showed better proficiency, emphasizing the importance of resource availability in language learning. These findings suggest the need for tailored interventions to address these factors for effective ESL education.

Table 2
Mann-Whitney Test Result for the Differences in the Grammar Proficiency of the Respondents when Classified as to Sex and Learning Materials Used

Compared Groups	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Z	p-value
Sex					
Male	65	61.34	3987.00	2.030	.042*
Female	71	75.06	5329.00		

Number of Learning Materials

1-2	87	61.70	5367.50	2.686	.007*
3 and more	49	80.58	3948.50		

*Significant @ 0.05

Kruskall-Wallis Test Result for the Differences in the Grammar Proficiency of the Respondents of when classified as to Monthly Family Income

The Kruskal-Wallis Test result in Table 3 reveals a non-significant difference in the grammar proficiency of the respondents when they are classified as to their monthly family income ($\chi^2 (2) = 4.046$; $p = .132$). The p-values are greater than 0.05, therefore the null hypothesis in this regard is not rejected. This means that, despite their numerical differences, the level of grammar proficiency of the respondents is practically the same. This indicates that the respondents' differences in their monthly family income do not significantly influence their grammar proficiency.

For instance, Madrunio et al. (2016) emphasized that limited resources could challenge efforts to enhance grammar proficiency, but these findings suggest that factors other than income—such as gender, educational environment, or teaching strategies—might have a stronger influence on grammar skills. Moreover, Serrano and Farin (2022) conducted a study on secondary students during the pandemic, which noted a connection between resource access and grammar proficiency. However, this study's results indicate that income disparities alone are not sufficient to produce statistically significant differences.

Table 3

Kruskall-Wallis Test Result for the Differences in the Grammar Proficiency of the Respondents of when classified as to Monthly Family Income

Compared Groups	N	Mean Rank	χ^2	df	p-value
Monthly Family Income					
10000 and below	90	69.89	4.046	2	.132
10001-20000	24	76.48			
Above 20000	22	54.09			

Conclusions

This study provided a comprehensive assessment of the grammar proficiency of Grade VII ESL learners at Tuyongan and Gama Integrated School during the School Year 2024-2025, with findings serving as a foundation for the development of a Syntax Learning Booklet.

The results revealed that the overall grammar proficiency of the respondents was classified as "Satisfactory." However, further analysis showed variations among different groups. Female learners demonstrated a higher level of grammar proficiency compared to male learners, indicating gender as a contributing factor to performance differences. Additionally, learners who had access to more English language materials exhibited stronger grammar proficiency, underscoring the importance of providing adequate learning resources to enhance language skills. On the other hand, while differences were observed across groups categorized by monthly family income, statistical tests revealed that economic background did not significantly influence grammar proficiency.

The study also examined whether these factors—sex, monthly family income, and number of English language materials—led to significant differences in grammar proficiency levels. Statistical tests confirmed that gender and access to learning materials had a significant impact, while family income did not.

Based on these findings, components for the Syntax Learning Booklet were thoughtfully developed to address identified grammar challenges. The booklet emphasizes inclusivity and resource accessibility, aiming to support learners regardless of gender or socioeconomic status. It includes practical exercises, targeted activities, and engaging content designed to enhance proficiency and meet the diverse needs of ESL learners.

This study highlights the importance of addressing disparities in access to resources and tailoring interventions to support diverse learners, offering valuable insights for improving language education and fostering greater achievement in grammar proficiency.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, several recommendations are proposed for educational stakeholders to enhance the grammar proficiency of ESL learners and support their language development.

For teachers, it is essential to adopt differentiated instruction tailored to the specific needs of learners. Notably, the study identified higher grammar proficiency among female learners, suggesting the need for targeted interventions to address gaps in male learners' performance. Teachers should also ensure equitable access to English language materials, as the availability of additional resources was found to significantly improve

grammar proficiency. Incorporating engaging and practical grammar exercises into lesson plans can further enhance learners' skills.

Curriculum developers are encouraged to design programs that prioritize the provision of diverse and accessible learning materials for all students. Curricula should also address specific grammar challenges identified in this study, incorporating inclusive and practical activities to meet the needs of learners from different backgrounds. Additionally, gender-sensitive approaches should be integrated into curriculum design to support balanced opportunities for male and female learners alike.

For future researchers, it is recommended to investigate other potential factors influencing grammar proficiency, such as teaching methods, classroom environments, or individual learner characteristics. Studies could also examine the long-term effects of increased access to learning materials on academic performance and evaluate the impact of interventions like the proposed Syntax Learning Booklet.

By implementing these recommendations, educational stakeholders can create an inclusive and resource-rich learning environment, ultimately improving the grammar proficiency and overall academic success of ESL learners.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study adhered to the ethical requirements of research to ensure the well-being and rights of participants. Prior to their inclusion, respondents were thoroughly informed about the procedures involved in the study and provided their consent by signing an agreement. The researcher also upheld ethical standards by prioritizing the privacy and confidentiality of participants throughout the research process.

Two measures were implemented to safeguard the privacy of respondents. First, confidentiality was strictly maintained, ensuring that any identifying information about participants was not disclosed to individuals who were not directly involved in the study. Second, the principle of anonymity was applied, requiring that participants' identities remain undisclosed and anonymous for the duration of the study. These measures exemplify the commitment to ethical research practices.

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